

Synergistic Effects of Dietary Tryptophan and Dip Vaccination in the Immune Response of European Seabass Juveniles

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Abstract

Vaccination is an effective, cost-efficient method to preventing disease outbreaks. However, vaccine procedures can induce adverse reactions due to stress, increasing plasma cortisol in the short term. In this context, tryptophan may prove to be fundamental as it has been demonstrated to have various desirable neuroendocrine attributes in different fish species. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate both short-term (3 days) and long-term (21 days) effects of dietary tryptophan supplementation on European seabass juveniles' (26.23 ± 7.22 g) response to vaccination and disease resistance to *Tenacibaculum maritimum*. The short-term tryptophan-fed fish exhibited increased hepatic superoxide dismutase and plasma cortisol levels, along with the downregulation of immune-related genes. Despite these changes, disease resistance was unaffected. When fish were later dip vaccinated, tryptophan prevented the stress-induced plasma cortisol increase and upregulated the gene expression of *igm*, suggesting tryptophan's role in enhancing vaccination efficiency by counteracting stress-associated effects. In the long term, the lowest supplementation dose counteracted vaccine-mediated reduced gene expression, and fish fed this diet showed a more modest molecular response. Overall, the findings suggest a complex interplay between tryptophan supplementation, immune responses, and vaccine efficiency in fish. Further research is necessary to clarify how tryptophan could consistently improve vaccine efficiency in aquaculture.